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A Novel Methodology Based on Orthogonal Projections for a Mobile Network Data Set Analysis

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ABSTRACT Nowadays, networks are at the center of the next industrial revolution. In fact, 5G in a short time will connect people, industries and things, so understanding how the network is performing its critical mission in this new paradigm is a key aspect. Network analytics increases the knowledge of the network and its users, leading the network managers to make smarter, data-driven decisions about the operations that they will execute in the network. In this article, a new methodology is introduced to analyze real data contained in a Call Details Record of a mobile network. With this novel methodology, the extraction of extreme points using the orthogonal projection decrease the complexity of the classification algorithm to obtain key information about network usage. Experimental results show how the proposed methodology selects and classifies network behavior patterns using a simple classification algorithm and how these patterns could be used to find, for instance, anomalies in the network, track human mobility, undertake network planning, detect events in the network, etc.

INDEX TERMS 5G, data analysis, mobile networks, network analytic.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Internet was originally designed in the mid-1970s to link together a small group of researchers. Nowadays, it is used by millions of people around the world mainly due to the appearance of mobile communications which has made it necessary to adapt traditional networks in order to accommodate mobile users. According to a recent forecast, there will be 28.5 billion networked devices by 2022, an increment of 37% compared with 201. In addition, global mobile data traffic will increase 7-fold between 2017 and 2022 [1].

The increase predicted in 2022 and beyond is driven by the emergence of 5G. The number of interconnected devices using heterogeneous technologies in order to seamlessly integrate multiple services and technologies will increase in a few years [2].

In many ways, 5G will be a key technology of the next industrial revolution, due to its capacity for high data

rates with ultra-low latency for applications in Industrial, Autonomous Vehicle, Tactile Internet, Robotics and Augmented reality (AR / Virtual Reality (VR) applications etc. The ability to support massive connectivity between diverse devices (sensors/gateways/controllers), with data processing on the edge of the network, and including the main characteristics of 5G such as high-bandwidth, low-latency or Mobile Edge Computing (MEC), requires from specialized nodes to acquire network information to data analytics to process all the information in order to infer improvements to the network [3]. In order to reduce costs, data analytics will play a critical role in the development of 5G and the network operations.

In order to improve the maintenance of the network and assure the availability of resources, network providers use network traffic monitoring systems to review, analyze and manage the network. These network traffic monitoring systems regularly collects extensive data about call volume, calling patterns and the location of the devices in order to analyze the information. This information is also useful in

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- [3] Y. Qiao, Z. Xing, Z. M. Fadlullah, J. Yang, and N. Kato, "Characterizing flow, application, and user behavior in mobile networks: A framework for mobile big data," *IEEE Wireless Commun.*, vol. 25, no. 1, pp. 40–49, Feb. 2018, doi: [10.1109/MWC.2018.1700186](https://doi.org/10.1109/MWC.2018.1700186).
- [4] M. von Mörner, "Application of call detail records—Chances and obstacles," *Transp. Res. Procedia*, vol. 25, pp. 2233–2241, Jan. 2017, doi: [10.1016/j.trpro.2017.05.429](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trpro.2017.05.429).
- [5] D. Naboulsi, M. Fiore, S. Ribot, and R. Stanica, "Large-scale mobile traffic analysis: A survey," *IEEE Commun. Surveys Tuts.*, vol. 18, no. 1, pp. 124–161, 1st Quart., 2016, doi: [10.1109/COMST.2015.2491361](https://doi.org/10.1109/COMST.2015.2491361).
- [6] K. H. Jones, H. Daniels, S. Heys, and D. V. Ford, "Challenges and potential opportunities of mobile phone call detail records in health research: Review," *JMIR mHealth uHealth*, vol. 6, no. 7, p. e161, 2018, doi: [10.2196/mhealth.9974](https://doi.org/10.2196/mhealth.9974).
- [7] K. Sultan, H. Ali, and Z. Zhang, "Call detail records driven anomaly detection and traffic prediction in mobile cellular networks," *IEEE Access*, vol. 6, pp. 41728–41737, 2018, doi: [10.1109/ACCESS.2018.2859756](https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2018.2859756).
- [8] Z. Zhao, S.-L. Shaw, Y. Xu, F. Lu, J. Chen, and L. Yin, "Understanding the bias of call detail records in human mobility research," *Int. J. of Geograph. Inf. Sci.*, vol. 30, no. 9, pp. 1738–1762, 2016, doi: [10.080/13658816.2015.1137298](https://doi.org/10.080/13658816.2015.1137298).
- [9] S. Phithakkitnukoon, T. W. Leong, Z. Smoreda, and P. Olivier, "Weather effects on mobile social interactions: A case study of mobile phone users in lisbon, portugal," *PLoS ONE*, vol. 7, no. 10, Oct. 2012, Art. no. e45745, doi: [10.1371/journal.pone.0045745](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0045745).
- [10] G. Barlacchi, M. De Nadai, R. Larcher, A. Casella, C. Chitic, G. Torrisi, F. Antonelli, A. Vespignani, A. Pentland, and B. Lepri, "A multi-source dataset of urban life in the city of Milan and the Province of Trentino," *Scientific Data - Nature*, vol. 2, Oct. 2015, Art. no. 150055, doi: [10.1038/sdata.2015.55](https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2015.55).
- [11] S. Roman, S. Axler, and F. W. Gehring, *Advanced Linear Algebra*, vol. 3. New York, NY, USA: Springer-Verlag, 2005.
- [12] H. K. Khalil, *Nonlinear Systems*. Upper Saddle River, NJ, USA: Prentice-Hall, 2002.
- [13] J. C. Harsanyi and C.-I. Chang, "Hyperspectral image classification and dimensionality reduction: An orthogonal subspace projection approach," *IEEE Trans. Geosci. Remote Sens.*, vol. 32, no. 4, pp. 779–785, Jul. 1994, doi: [10.1109/36.298007](https://doi.org/10.1109/36.298007).
- [14] Z. Bu, H. Li, C. Zhang, J. Cao, A. Li, and Y. Shi, "Graph K -means based on Leader identification, dynamic game and opinion dynamics," *IEEE Trans. Knowl. Data Eng.*, to be published, doi: [10.1109/TKDE.2019.2903712](https://doi.org/10.1109/TKDE.2019.2903712).
- [15] Z. Bu, Y. Wang, H. Li, J. Jiang, Z. Wu, and J. Cao, "Link prediction in temporal networks: Integrating survival analysis and game theory," *Inf. Sci.*, vol. 498, pp. 41–61, Sep. 2019, doi: [10.1016/j.ins.2019.05.050](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ins.2019.05.050).
- [16] J. G. Andrews, S. Buzzi, W. Choi, S. V. Hanly, A. Lozano, A. C. Soong, and J. C. Zhang, "What will 5G be?" *IEEE J. Sel. Areas Commun.*, vol. 32, no. 6, pp. 1065–1082, Jun. 2014, doi: [10.1109/JSAC.2014.2328098](https://doi.org/10.1109/JSAC.2014.2328098).
- [17] A. Plaza, P. Martinez, R. Perez, and J. Plaza, "Spatial/spectral endmember extraction by multidimensional morphological operations," *IEEE Trans. Geosci. Remote Sens.*, vol. 40, no. 9, pp. 2025–2041, Sep. 2002, doi: [10.1109/TGRS.2002.802494](https://doi.org/10.1109/TGRS.2002.802494).
- [18] C. D. Meyer, *Matrix Analysis and Applied Linear Algebra*, vol. 71. Philadelphia, PA, USA: SIAM, 2000.
- [19] S. Lopez, P. Horstrand, G. M. Callico, J. F. Lopez, and R. Sarmiento, "A low-computational-complexity algorithm for hyperspectral endmember extraction: Modified vertex component analysis," *IEEE Geosci. Remote Sens. Lett.*, vol. 9, no. 3, pp. 502–506, May 2012.
- [20] D. Bega, M. Gramaglia, C. J. Bernardos Cano, A. Banchs, and X. Costa-Perez, "Toward the network of the future: From enabling technologies to 5G concepts," *Trans. Emerg. Telecommun. Technol.*, vol. 28, no. 8, Aug. 2017, Art. no. e3205, doi: [10.1002/ett.3205](https://doi.org/10.1002/ett.3205).

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